

THE NEED OF UZBEK LEARNERS TO USE LANGUAGE CORPUS WHILE LEARNING LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article covers data about corpus linguistics, including its history, criteria for building one, and potential applications in language instruction. It also looks at the issues of Uzbek learners that have arisen during the process of learning a foreign language and gives instances of how the corpus has been used to teach foreign languages

Keywords: corpus linguistics, history, definition, teaching foreign language, education system, challenges, language corpus

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The educational system of many governments has been impacted by the globalization process, which is occurring on a global scale. Interest in learning new languages rises as there is a greater demand for intercultural communication amongst representatives of other ethnicities. Besides that, learning and teaching languages alongside the development of language and technology is huge task in front of many linguists. Furthermore, there is a high demand to learn foreign languages effectively for Uzbek learners and during the last decade new innovative and incredibly promising way to organize the process of teaching foreign languages has emerged. This area of linguistics allows students to access language data directly and it provides learners to learn languages far more successfully when using the corpora, which gives them the chance to determine for themselves the meanings of words, phrases, and grammar rules.

One of the divisions of linguistics is corpus linguistics, which is tasked with gathering and analyzing corpora of writings. The phrase was first used in science in the 1960s in relation to the start of corpora production, and since the 1980s, thanks to computer technology, this field has started to gain momentum. It wasn't until the 1980s that the phrase "corpus linguistics" was coined, despite the fact that the techniques utilized in this field were initially developed in the early 1960s. Initially founded on the English language, corpus linguistics quickly expanded to include languages other than English. Corpus linguistics has been defined differently by many scholars. According to Vladimir Plungyan who is a Doctor of Philology, professor, academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences defines the importance of this concept as "The corpus of language and the science that is associated with

this, corpus linguistics, is such a topic, an area that very quickly burst into the life of linguists in approximately late XX - early XXI century. If we want to name a field of linguistics that is ultramodern by definition, then the first thing that comes to mind is just the linguistics of the corpus”.

According to N.V. Kozlova, a corpus is an electronic collection of texts in one or more languages that was produced using specific criteria. According to her, despite being a collection of written or spoken texts, the corpus differs from regular texts in that it has been digitized, meaning that the texts have been electronically analyzed, tagged specifically, stored electronically, and annotated linguistically to organize the information.

In order to evaluate the realities of the language in its natural condition over the last 10–15 years, scholars in the teaching of foreign languages have used huge text corpora. The quality of the published language manuals has substantially improved because to these corpora of texts. New corpus studies describe and experimentally reasonably examine what people actually say, as opposed to old rules on how to use the language. Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English, which was published in 2000, as well as the experience of critically rethinking the tenets of descriptive English grammar deserve special mention. These new dictionaries were produced using corpus linguistics techniques. Other examples include Collins, Oxford, and Longman.

Coming to the goal of the language corpus, it demonstrates how linguistic components function in their actual context of use. The corpus can provide information on the frequency of word forms, lexical units, and grammatical categories as well as information on changes in frequency, context changes over time, the behavior of linguistic units used by different authors, the co-occurrence of lexical units, and other aspects of their compatibility and management.

Why do the learners need to use a corpus and how it can be used while learning a language? Modern computerized education is moving away from the just presentation of teaching material. Methods that have been used in teaching and learning requires a creative approach and self-education, learner-centered teaching. The person studying a foreign language reads the corpus text (or portion of text) on their own. He made an assumption regarding the significance of one or more textual components, and his initial assumptions led to his initial conclusions. The learner will learn specific knowledge and abilities that will be retained in his memory far longer than the information learned from standard textbooks by analyzing the following piece of material and drawing more confident conclusions. Using these methods with the help of corpus provides efficient learning for Uzbek learners and helps to overcome language learning issues.

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